

D5.5 - Implementation and validation of RESTORE Use-Case II: Integration of different heat sources in DH of Cement Industry

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Summary

This deliverable presents the activities and outcomes of Task 5.4 within RESTORE EU project, which focuses on demonstrating the performance and replicability of the RESTORE integrated system in several facilities. The task consists of the implementation, optimization, and validation of six real use-cases through their digital representations, using the RESTORE Simulation Web Platform (IPSE GO). These virtual models aim to replicate real district heating and cooling (DHC) networks across diverse industrial and geographical contexts in Europe, including biomass and solar systems, cement and paper industries, steelworks, geothermal applications, and university campuses.

Deliverable D5.5 deals with the implementation and validation of RESTORE Use-Case II: Integration of different heat sources in DH of Cement Industry, via the simulation web-platform.

The document details the methodological framework used to implement the Use Case (Subtasks 5.4.2), drawing on technical input from WP1 to WP4, and presenting simulation models for Use-Case II within the RESTORE Virtual Tool, resulting from the integration of the RESTORE concept in DH coupled to the Cement Industry. For each use-case, the partners defined specific system boundaries, components, and operational conditions, which were then simulated and optimized in the platform. The work provides a technical validation of the RESTORE. Ultimately, the insights gathered here serve as a cornerstone for developing large-scale replication strategies in Task 5.5, facilitating broader deployment of RESTORE technologies across Europe.

The economic and environmental analyses are included in the upcoming deliverables of Tasks 1.6 and 1.7. Therefore, they are not covered in this report, as they are the main focus of those deliverables, and their inclusion here would be repetitive and redundant.

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1. Introduction

Subtask 5.4.2 (Use-Case II - Integration of different heat sources in DH of Cement Industry) addresses the implementation and virtual replication of the RESTORE TCES concept within a Cement Plant located in the municipality of Gmunden, Austria. The objective is to identify the waste heat sources in the facility and to integrate them into the RESTORE simulation framework to assess their performance under different operational conditions and control strategies.

Led by CENER, with the technical support of SIMTECH, the work involves defining the system mass and heat balances integration, available renewable energy sources and thermal chemical energy storage (TCES) configuration. The model is implemented within the IPSE GO platform, enabling interactive simulation, control testing, and optimization of system sizing and parameters involved.

This document is structured to present a comprehensive analysis of the implementation of the User Case. It begins with a description of the baseline plant, including its technical background and configuration (Section 2). Section 3 focuses on the integration of the RESTORE TCES system, detailing the use-case definition, the role of the IPSE Go Platform, the input data (including assumptions and refinements), and the virtual implementation steps. Section 4 presents the results, encompassing the process simulations. The document concludes with key findings (Section 5) and references (Section 6).

2. Baseline Plant: Gmunden Cement Plant

The cement industry is a key part of today's civilization. Due to the climate crisis, the cement process is under strong pressure for reducing CO₂-emissions and optimizing energy efficiency. The initial calcination reaction in the production of cement is responsible for about 4% of global CO₂ emissions. The overall process is responsible for about 8% of global CO₂ emissions [1], as the cement kiln in which the reaction occurs is typically fired by coal or petroleum coke due to the luminous flame required to heat the kiln by radiant heat transfer at 2000 °C. As a result, the production of cement has a high-impact potential to climate change.

This situation creates a significant opportunity for carbonization strategies—innovative processes and technologies aimed at capturing, storing, or utilizing carbon dioxide (CO₂). Due to this reason, the feasibility of the implementation of the RESTORE solution in a cement producing plant has been chosen as a use case study.

General information about the Use-Case II and its plant, is described in the public documentation of “RESTORE Use-Cases Modelling” concerning WP5 Task T5.4 implementation, optimization, management & validation of the six RESTORE Use-Cases, using the Simulation Web Platform”, available in the project's Zenodo Community account (<https://zenodo.org/communities/101036766/records>) [2].

2.1. Plant description

The cement plant under analysis is located in Gmunden, Austria, and operates as part of the [Rohrdorfer Group](#), an established company in the cement and building materials industry in Central Europe. This plant is specialized in the production of clinker, the intermediate product in the manufacturing process of Portland cement. Clinker is formed - as it will be explained in detail further in the document – by sintering limestone and other raw materials at high temperatures and serves as the main component in cement production.

With a daily production capacity of approximately 1900 tonnes of cement clinker, the Gmunden plant plays a key role in regional and international cement supply. In addition to the production capability, due to the thermal nature of the industry, the plant is equipped with a district heating connection. This connection enables the plant to supply exceeding thermal energy produced in the clinker burning process to the local heating network, improving energy efficiency and contributing to the decarbonization of the surrounding community's energy use.

However, the operation of the district heating network is strongly dependent on the continuous and stable generation of excess thermal energy during the clinker production process. Since the heat recovery potential is directly linked to the kiln's operational schedule and efficiency, any variations in clinker output, shutdowns, or maintenance activities can significantly impact the availability of heat for the district heating system. Therefore, storing heat becomes a crucial strategy to decouple heat generation from immediate demand. By integrating the RESTORE thermochemical energy storage system, the plant can accumulate excess heat during periods of high clinker production and release it when production is reduced or temporarily halted.

2.1.1. Cement production process

The cement production process will be briefly explained below [3]:

1 Quarry, Crusher	6 Process Filter	11 Clinker Cooler	16 Cement Grinding
2 Blending Beds	7 Homogenization Silos	12 Clinker Storage	17 Additives for Grinding
3 Additives / Aggregates	8 Cyclone Preheater	13 Coal Grinding	18 Cement Mixer
4 Raw Material Grinding	9 Kiln System	14 Plastic Shredding	19 Cement Silos
5 Gas Conditioning	10 Calciner	15 Sewage Sludge	20 Stack / Chimney

Figure 1. Cement production process flow diagram.

The extraction and preparation of the raw material. (1 → 7)

Quarries are exploited by controlled blasting, in the case of hard materials such as limestone and slate, while in the case of soft materials (clays and marls) excavators are used for their extraction. Once the material has been extracted and classified, it is crushed to a suitable granulometry for the grinding product and transferred to the factory by conveyor belts or trucks for storage in the pre-homogenization park. The crushed material is stored in uniform layers to be subsequently selected in a controlled manner. Pre-homogenization allows the

appropriate dosage of the different components to be prepared, reducing their variability. These materials are ground to reduce their size and thus promote their firing in the oven.

Clinker production (8 → 12)

The cyclone preheater heats the raw material before firing. It descends through the tower while kiln gases rise in counter-current, preheating it to 1000 °C before entering the kiln. As the flour moves through the kiln, the temperature rises to 1500 °C, triggering the chemical reactions that produce clinker. The kiln's main flame burns at 2000 °C to achieve the necessary temperatures for firing the raw materials and clinker production. The clinker exits the kiln and enters the cooler, where cold air is injected to reduce its temperature from 1400°C to 100°C. The hot air produced is then reintroduced into the kiln to aid combustion, enhancing the process's energy efficiency.

Clinker grinding and cement manufacturing (13 → 19)

The clinker is mixed with plaster and additions inside a cement mill. The cement is stored in silos, separated according to its classes. The cement is bagged or unloaded into a tanker truck for transport by road or rail.

2.1.1. Working period and Shutdown

In simplified terms, the plant operated at full capacity for approximately 10 months of the year. It was completely shut down during December and January. Throughout the remaining 10 months, operations were only interrupted due to technical issues. These interruptions can vary year by year. In the year under review (around 2018), there was one major stoppage lasting 48 hours, along with approximately six other stoppages ranging from 2 to 12 hours each. For the use case studied the stoppages will be considered as six stoppages of an average of 7 hours. This data can be summarized in the following table:

Working Period and Shutdown Summary¹			
Category	Description	Hours	Comment
Shutdown	Planned shutdown	1464	December and January (2 months)
	1 major stoppage	48	Unplanned
	6 stoppages (av. 7h)	42	Unplanned
Total shutdown time	-	1554	Includes planned + unplanned
Working period	-	7206	Remaining time (based on 8760 h/year)

¹ Data extracted from the Gmunden Cement plant behaviour in the year 2018.

3. RESTORE TCES Integration

As mentioned above, the RESTORE solution will be integrated to make use of the surplus thermal energy, capturing it in a thermochemical energy storage (TCES) and releasing it when necessary.

3.1. Use Case definition

The Use Case 2 studies the implementation of the RESTORE concept in the Gmunden cement plant, located in Austria. The goal of the solution is to ensure the thermal energy supply of the existing district heating, regardless of the cement plant working periods without using fossil fuels of external energy sources.

The system takes advantage of the significant waste heat generated during the working period of the factory in the cement production process. This thermal energy, which would otherwise be dissipated, is stored in the RESTORE thermochemical reactor in form of chemical energy through an endothermic reaction (copper sulphate dehydration). The solution is designed in such a way that can discharge the stored energy during the factory shutdown months, plus the stoppages described in the previous chapter. It is important to emphasize that the proposed system is particularly valuable during the critical hours of the day when ambient temperatures are at their lowest and solar radiation is insufficient. Therefore, our solution is tailored to provide heat predominantly during night periods, ensuring both energy efficiency and comfort. The energy release is performed reversing the charging reaction in the TCES using an exothermic reaction (copper sulphate hydration).

3.2. IPSE Go Platform

The IPSE Go Platform is a web-based simulation and optimization environment designed to support the virtual implementation of complex energy systems. Within the RESTORE project, it plays a central role in the digital representation and testing of six real-world use-cases, each reflecting distinct district heating and cooling (DHC) configurations. The platform allows users to model, simulate, and optimize integrated energy systems combining components such as thermochemical storage, renewable heat sources, and thermodynamic cycles.

One of the core strengths of IPSE Go lies in its flexibility and modular design. It supports the integration of a wide variety of components and subsystems, enabling partners to replicate specific operational settings and boundary conditions from each use-case. For each virtual scenario, the platform facilitates the configuration of heat sources, sinks, storage units, and control strategies, ensuring that the simulation mirrors the physical dynamics of the real installation as accurately as possible.

In addition to basic system modelling, IPSE Go incorporates advanced optimization tools that help evaluate the system's performance under different operational parameters. Users can simulate dynamic behaviour over time, analyse energy flows, and test alternative layouts or control algorithms. This supports the identification of the most effective technical solutions for each local context and ensures that the RESTORE concept is not only functional but also efficient and scalable.

The platform also plays a key role in promoting replicability and transparency across the project. Its cloud-based nature facilitates collaboration between project partners, enabling remote access, version tracking, and shared testing environments. By consolidating all use-cases in a unified digital workspace, IPSE Go enables systematic benchmarking, comparison, and validation of the RESTORE solution across diverse European settings.

3.3. Input Data

This section outlines the basic data used in the analysis. It includes the main waste heat sources identified in the cement production process, as well as the assumptions made to simplify the evaluation. These inputs are used as the starting point for further calculations and assessments.

3.3.1. Waste heat sources

To be able to size the loading system and storage, it is necessary to identify and quantify the main sources of waste heat of the plant under analysis. The main points of heat loss are indicated in the process diagram:

Figure 2. Waste heat source identification in the process flow diagram.

The estimated values are presented and summarized in the following table:

Waste heat sources [4]			
WH	Power (MW _{th})	Temperature (°C)	Medium
A	10	400	Dust loaded flue gas
B	28.6	130	Flue gas to stack
C	3	100	Cement mill

To determine the mass flows associated with the described waste heat (WH) source, the identified thermal power has been used in conjunction with a temperature difference ranging from 25 °C (ambient) to the specified source temperature.

3.3.2. Assumptions

With the intention of simplifying the calculations and the model, several assumptions have been considered concerning the studied plant:

Waste heat:

- The waste heat flue gas will be considered as dry air with ideal gas behaviour.
- The workload in the cement factory remains constant over time, and consequently, so does the waste heat.

Working period:

- The working period and stops recorded in 2018 (see section 2.1.1) will be considered as the standard behaviour of the plant.

District heating:

- A DH power supply time of 12h per day is considered, running at night, when the ambient temperatures are at their lowest and the solution is more valuable. This will be applied for the 2-month shutdown and the 48h stop, not for the rest of the stoppages. This makes a **total discharge time of 798 h**.

Storage dimensioning:

- For the storage dimensioning, 732 h will be considered, corresponding to the 2-month shut down, as the other seven stoppages will not be consecutive to the 2-month shutdown.

3.4. IPSE GO Virtual Use-Case II implementation

This section describes how the virtual use-case II (UC2) is set up and implemented in IPSE GO. It includes the definition of the UC2 model, as well as the configurations used for the charge mode and discharge mode. These steps are essential to simulate the system behaviour and evaluate its performance under the given operating conditions.

3.4.1. UC2 Model definition

The RESTORE solution demonstrates strong suitability for seasonal thermal energy storage, particularly in industrial contexts such as the Gmunden cement plant. Its design enables the recovery and storage of high-temperature waste heat during active production periods, which can then be released on demand to supply thermal energy to a district heating (DH) network—even during the factory's seasonal shutdowns or unplanned stoppages.

The selected waste heat source, designated as Source 'A' in the previous summary, originates from a dust-laden flue gas stream at approximately 400 °C, making it an excellent candidate for driving thermochemical reactions due to its high thermal quality.

In this configuration, cyclopentane has been chosen as the working fluid for both the Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) and heat pump components, due to its favorable thermodynamic properties under the expected operating conditions.

During the charging phase, the waste heat is used to power the endothermic dehydration of copper sulphate (CuSO_4), the selected thermochemical material (TCM). This process stores thermal energy in the form of chemical potential. The discharging phase then reverses this reaction: when water is reintroduced, the exothermic hydration of CuSO_4 occurs, releasing the stored energy as heat.

This chemical storage mechanism enables flexible and dispatchable heat delivery, decoupling heat generation from industrial production schedules. As a result, the RESTORE system can maintain a consistent heat supply to the DH network throughout the year, even during months when the cement plant is not operating—effectively bridging the gap between intermittent industrial activity and continuous thermal demand.

3.4.2. The Charging Mode

The charging mode model represents the waste heat utilization for reactor thermochemical material (TCM) dehydration to store energy. The model can be divided into three main sections, such as an intermediate Rankine cycle, the heat pump (HP) with reheating, and the one that corresponds to the dehydration of TCM in the TCES.

Figure 3. Charging mode model.

The three main sections of the charging model are explained below:

3.4.2.1. TCM dehydration

When dehydrating thermochemical material (TCM), an endothermic reaction occurs, storing energy in form of chemical potential energy. This is modelled as illustrated in Figure 4:

Figure 4. Charging mode model. TCM dehydration

The hydrated TCM flows from storage (green stream) until it reaches a mixer (1), where it is combined with a thermal oil input. After this, it undergoes a preheating stage (2) that brings the TCM to the ideal temperature required for the reaction to occur.

Once properly tempered, the mixture is introduced into the thermochemical reactor. Inside the reactor (3), the dehydration reaction of the TCM takes place, absorbing heat at 125 °C. As a result, water is released (blue stream) and exits the reactor. A submodel of a heat sink (4) is used to quantify the energy delivered as heat through this outgoing water stream.

The dehydrated TCM, which exits the reactor at high temperature, then passes through a heat exchanger (5). Here, part of its heat is recovered and used to preheat the incoming TCM before it enters the reactor.

Following heat exchange, the TCM flows into a separator (6). This component divides the stream into two parts: one consisting purely of thermal oil—which rejoins the TCM stream entering from storage—and the other consisting of TCM directed back to storage. Another heat sink submodel (7) is used here to estimate the thermal energy lost in the TCM returning to storage.

The thermal fluid circuit (represented in orange) is a simplified or “dummy” circuit that serves only to model the heat exchange between the reactor output and the reactants.

As will be detailed later in the document, the discharge power of the reactor is defined as 500 kW_{th}. To ensure optimal efficiency of the reactor heat exchanger with the rest of the system, it has been decided to match the charging power to this same value: 500 kW_{th}. This

symmetry ensures that the required amount of TCM can be processed to meet the 798 hours of thermal supply targeted in the use case.

The assumed conversion fraction of the TCM in the reactor is 0.95 kg/kg, and the pressure drop across the reactor is considered negligible.

3.4.2.1. Intermediate Rankine cycle

The heat pump evaporator has certain temperature limitations that do not allow direct heat exchange between the hot gas coming from the industry and the cycle. For this reason, it has been decided to install an intermediate cycle, which will transfer the heat from the gas to the water (from district heating) which, then, will be connected to the evaporator of the heat pump used to charge the TCES.

Given the high temperature of the available waste heat, this configuration also enables the integration of a power generation system during the charging phase. The excess thermal energy—beyond what is required for heat pump operation—can be exploited to produce additional electricity and heat (this last delivered to the DH network). This makes the most of the thermal potential of the waste heat from the cement plant and increases the overall efficiency of the system by delivering both heat and electricity from a single energy input, as well as storing energy in the TCES.

Figure 5. Charging mode model. Intermediate Rankine cycle

The cycle used is a simple Rankine cycle, with cyclopentane as working fluid. The waste heat gas enters the heat exchanger at 400 °C and the cycle delivers the heat to a water stream that exits the condenser at 70 °C a suitable temperature for the HP cycle.

The following are the main parameters defined for the intermediate Rankine cycle model for RESTORE charging:

Evaporator (1)			
Variable	Description	Value	Unit
nSlices	Number of slices used in the external profile calculation functions	10	[-]
dt_sub	Subcooling temperature	0.01	[°C]
delta_p_hot	Pressure drop hot side	0.03	[bar]
delta_p_cold	Pressure drop cold side	0.1	[bar]
heat_loss	Percentage of heat lost to the surroundings	0	[%]
dt_in	Temperature difference at the inlet of the cooling stream	54	[°C]

Condenser (2)			
Variable	Description	Value	Unit
nSlices	Number of slices used in the external profile calculation functions	10	[-]
dt_sub	Subcooling temperature	0.01	[°C]
delta_p_hot	Pressure drop hot side	0.03	[bar]
delta_p_cold	Pressure drop cold side	0.1	[bar]
heat_loss	Percentage of heat lost to the surroundings	0	[%]
dt_in	Temperature difference at the inlet of the cooling stream	40	[°C]

Non reversible turbine (3)			
Variable	Description	Value	Unit
eta_s	Isentropic efficiency	0.8	[-]

Pump (4)			
Variable	Description	Value	Unit
eta_s	Isentropic efficiency	0.7	[-]

3.4.2.2. Heat pump

The excess heat from the cement plant gases is used for the heat pump to feed the TCM endothermic dehydration reaction, storing the energy.

Figure 6. Charging mode model. Heat Pump.

The TCES charging phase is based on a heat pump cycle with conventional reheating (2), in which cyclopentane is used as the working fluid. This setup enables efficient transfer of thermal energy required for the endothermic reaction in the thermochemical storage system.

In this model, the condenser is represented as a heat exchanger (4) connected to a wall at a constant temperature. The temperature of this wall is fixed at 125 °C, which corresponds to the temperature dictated by the dehydration reaction of CuSO_4 occurring in the thermochemical reactor.

The organic working fluid (cyclopentane) enters the heat exchanger at 135 °C, delivering the necessary heat for the dehydration process. This ensures effective thermal coupling between the heat pump and the reactor.

For modeling purposes, an absolute pressure loss of 0.05 bar has been considered, along with a charging heat transfer rate of 500 kW, which aligns with the predefined charging power for the system.

The following are the main parameters defined for the heat pump model for RESTORE charging:

Evaporator (1)			
Variable	Description	Value	Unit
nSlices	Number of slices used in the external profile calculation functions	10	[-]
delta_p_hot	Pressure drop hot side	0.1	[bar]
delta_p_cold	Pressure drop cold side	0.1	[bar]
heat_loss	Percentage of heat lost to the surroundings	0	[%]
dt_in	Temperature difference at the inlet of the cooling stream	3	[°C]

Reheat heat exchanger (2)			
Variable	Description	Value	Unit
nSlices	Number of slices used in the external profile calculation functions	10	[-]
delta_p_hot	Pressure drop hot side	0.2	[bar]
delta_p_cold	Pressure drop cold side	0.05	[bar]
heat_loss	Percentage of heat lost to the surroundings	0	[%]
dt_in	Temperature difference at the inlet of the cooling stream	5	[°C]

Non reversible compressor (3)			
Variable	Description	Value	Unit
eta_s	Isentropic efficiency	0.8	[-]

3.4.3. The Discharging Mode

The discharging mode model represents the TCM hydration reaction use to release the previously stored energy in form of heat later delivered to a district heating, generating electricity in the process. The discharging mode model can be divided into two main sections: the reversible organic Rankine cycle (rORC) with reheating, and the one that corresponds to the hydration of TCM in the TCES.

Figure 7. Discharging mode model.

The two main sections of the discharging mode model are explained in the sequel:

3.4.3.1. TCM hydration

When the thermochemical material (TCM) is hydrated, an exothermic reaction occurs, releasing the stored energy, as illustrated in Figure 8:

The dehydrated thermochemical material (TCM) flows from storage (green stream) to a mixer (1), where it is combined with a thermal oil supply. Afterward, the mixture undergoes a preheating phase (2) that brings the TCM to the optimal temperature required for the chemical reaction.

Simultaneously, a preheated (3) water stream (blue stream) is also supplied to the reactor (4) in a similar manner as the TCM. Both streams are then introduced into the thermochemical reactor, where the hydration reaction of the TCM occurs. This reaction is exothermic, releasing heat at a temperature of approximately 105 °C.

Figure 8. Discharging mode model. TCM hydration.

The hydrated TCM, exiting the reactor at elevated temperature, flows through a heat exchanger (5), which recovers part of the heat to preheat both the incoming water and TCM streams before they enter the reactor. This increases the thermal efficiency of the cycle.

After the heat exchanger, the material enters a separator (6) that splits the flow into two streams: one consisting solely of thermal oil, which is recirculated to rejoin the incoming TCM from storage, and the other stream directed back to storage as hydrated TCM. A heat sink submodel (7) is used here to quantify the thermal energy loss associated with the TCM returning to storage.

The thermal fluid circuit (orange stream) is a dummy loop, included in the model solely to represent the heat exchange between the reactor output and the reactants entering the system.

To meet the thermal demand over a 61-day supply period—assuming 12 hours per day of discharge, plus the periods when the plant is offline (a total of 798 hours)—the discharge power of the TCES system must match the energy requirements. A discharge power of 500 kW_{th} has been determined as sufficient, based on a reasonable amount of TCM to be handled and stored within the system.

3.4.3.2. Organic Rankine Cycle

The heat generated from the reaction is used with the help of an organic Rankine cycle, from which electrical power and heat are extracted for the district heating of Gmunden.

Figure 9. Discharging mode model. Organic Rankine Cycle.

The TCES discharging phase is based on a organic Rankine cycle (ORC) with conventional reheating, where cyclopentane is used as the working fluid. The evaporator in this model is represented as a heat exchanger connected to a wall at a constant temperature (5). In this case, the wall temperature is fixed at 105 °C, which is determined by the chemical reaction occurred in the reactor. The organic fluid exits the heat exchanger at 100 °C to extracting the heat generated in the hydration of CuSO_4 . An absolute pressure loss of 0.05 bar and a heat transfer of 500 kW have been considered as the determined discharging power. The temperature difference considered for the inlet and outlet of the DH connection is from 35 to 55 °C.

The following tables present the main parameters defined for the heat pump model for RESTORE discharging:

Condenser (1)			
Variable	Description	Value	Unit
nSlices	Number of slices used in the external profile calculation functions	10	[-]
dt_sub	Subcooling temperature	0.01	[°C]
delta_p_hot	Pressure drop hot side	0.03	[bar]
delta_p_cold	Pressure drop cold side	0.1	[bar]
heat_loss	Percentage of heat lost to the surroundings	0	[%]
dt_in	Temperature difference at the inlet of the cooling stream	35	[°C]

Reheat heat exchanger (2)			
Variable	Description	Value	Unit
nSlices	Number of slices used in the external profile calculation functions	10	[-]
delta_p_hot	Pressure drop hot side	0.03	[bar]
delta_p_cold	Pressure drop cold side	0.1	[bar]
heat_loss	Percentage of heat lost to the surroundings	0	[%]
dt_in	Temperature difference at the inlet of the cooling stream	5	[°C]

Non reversible turbine (3)			
Variable	Description	Value	Unit
eta_s	Isentropic efficiency	0.8	[-]

Pump (4)			
Variable	Description	Value	Unit
eta_s	Isentropic efficiency	0.7	[-]

4. Results

This section presents the main outcomes of the implementation of the virtual Use-Case II, with the description of the Process Simulations, divided into two parts: 1. Including results from the charging mode scenario; and 2. Respective to the results of the discharging mode scenario. Together, these results provide insights into the technical feasibility of the proposed system.

4.1. Process Simulations

This part presents the results of the system simulations under different operating modes. It is divided into charge mode and discharge mode. The simulations were carried out using the defined virtual model and provide insights into the energy flows, temperature levels, and overall system behaviour during each phase.

4.1.1. Charging Mode

The overall results concerning the charging phase of the model, can be summarized by the energy balance data presented in the following table:

Charging energy balance		
Equivalent operation Hours (charging)	6326.3	[h]
TCM produced	12923	[tn]
Waste heat consumed	47398	[MWh]
Heat delivered to TCES	3163	[MWh]
Heat delivered to DH	38712	[MWh]
TCES Steam heat produced	2217	[MWh]
Electricity produced	5521	[MWh]

Note that the charging time, 263 days or 8.6 months approximately, is a feasible time, since added to the 2 months of discharge operation, they add up to a period of time less than a year, allowing to operate with 2 extra months of maintenance or some other purpose.

Concerning the mass balance in the TCM storage system, we obtain the following compositions and mass flows:

Thermochemical material balance					
TCM FLOW	Mass flow (kg/h)	w_Mat1 (kg/kg)	w_Mat2 (kg/kg)	w_Oil (kg/kg)	w_Water (kg/kg)
FROM STORAGE	2527.9	0.7	0	0.3	0
TO STORAGE	2042.7	0.0433	0.5854	0.3713	0

The intermediate Rankine cycle and heat pump cycle are presented below, in temperature-entropy graphs and another illustrating the behaviour of pressure as a function of enthalpy:

Figure 10. Charging mode, Intermediate Rankine cycle. T-S diagram.

Figure 11. Charging mode, Intermediate Rankine cycle. P-H diagram.

Figure 12. Charging mode, Heat Pump. T-S diagram.

Figure 13. Charging mode, Heat Pump. P-H diagram.

The results obtained for the charging phase, both for the intermediate Rankine cycle and the heat pump cycle can be summarized by the data presented in the following table:

Intermediate Rankine cycle (Charging)		
Cycle El. Power Output	996.85	[kW]
Condenser Heat to DH and TCES	6495.34	[kW]
Evaporator Heat Transfer	7492,18	[kW]
Gross Cycle Efficiency	13.94	[%]
Net Cycle Efficiency	13.31	[%]
Pump Mass Flow	15.32	[kg/s]
Condenser U*A	295.73	[kW/K]
Evaporator U*A	61.97	[kW/K]

Heat Pump (Charging)		
Cycle El. Power Input	123.90	[kW]
Condenser Heat to Reactor	500.00	[kW]
Evaporator Heat Transfer	7492	[kW]
COP	4.04	[-]
Compressor Pressure Ratio	5.9	[-]
Compressor Mass Flow	1.162	[kg/s]
Compressor Inlet Volumetric Flow	360.09	[l/s]
Compressor Outlet Volumetric Flow	65.49	[l/s]
Condenser U*A	16.24	[kW/K]
Evaporator U*A	61.97	[kW/K]
Recuperator U*A	10.03	[kW/K]

4.1.2. Discharge Mode

The overall results concerning the discharging phase of the model, can be summarized in the following table:

Discharging energy balance		
Duration discharging	798	[h]
TCM consumed	12923	[tn]
El energy produced	22.933	[MWh]
Heat produced	5259	[MWh]

Concerning the mass balance in the TCM storage system, we obtain the following compositions and mass flows:

Thermochemical material balance					
TCM FLOW	Mass flow (kg/h)	w_Mat1 (kg/kg)	w_Mat2 (kg/kg)	w_Oil (kg/kg)	w_Water (kg/kg)
FROM STORAGE	16193.941	0.0433	0.5854	0.3713	0
TO STORAGE	20117.047	0.6973	0	0.2989	0.0038

The ORC is presented below, in a temperature-entropy graph and another illustrating the behaviour of pressure as a function of enthalpy:

Figure 14. Discharging mode. T-S diagram.

Figure 15. Discharging mode. P-H diagram.

The results obtained from the ORC can be summarized in the following table:

Organic Rankine Cycle (Discharging)		
Cycle El. Power Output	29.35	[kW]
Net El. Power Output	28.74	[kW]
Evaporator Heat from Reactor	500.00	[kW]
Condenser Heat Transfer	471.26	[kW]
Gross Cycle Efficiency	5.87	%
Net Cycle Efficiency	5.75	%
Turbine Pressure Ratio	2.11	[-]
Turbine Mass Flow	1.2385	[kg/s]
Turbine Inlet Volumetric Flow	118.8729	[l/s]
Turbine Outlet Volumetric Flow	249.1020	[l/s]
Evaporator U*A	34.7471	[kW/K]
Condenser U*A	19.3803	[kW/K]
Recuperator U*A	1.5208	[kW/K]

5. Conclusions

Key conclusions from RESTORE UC2 Gmunden Use Case are summarized and categorized as follows. Note that the economic and environmental analyses are included in the upcoming deliverables of Tasks 1.6 and 1.7. Therefore, they are not covered in this report, as they are the main focus of those deliverables, and their inclusion here would be repetitive and redundant.

Specific conclusions about integration and feasibility:

- **Non-used thermal energy sources identification (waste heat).** The Use Case has identified the possible storage of approximately **300 GWh/year** that is currently not utilized by the facilities and dissipated into the ambient environment in the form of flue gas or cement mill.
- **The high temperature of the waste heat gases (~400 °C) technological challenge.** This issue has been successfully addressed through the implementation of an intermediate cycle, which significantly improves the overall utilization of waste heat by enabling the co-production of electricity and the supply of energy to the district heating network, even during the charging phase of the TCES.
- **Favourable operating conditions for TCES in cement production.** The cement industry, due to its stable and continuous production process, offers favourable conditions for the optimal sizing of the equipment required for TCES integration. Furthermore, this operational stability simplifies the charging process of the storage system, as it ideally receives a steady flow of heat throughout the charging phase.
- **Full-year simulation demonstrates operational viability.** The IPSE Go model successfully simulates **6326.3 hours of charging** and **798 hours of discharging**, confirming that the TCES system can be operated consistently within real plant conditions.
- **ORC integration validated with detailed thermodynamic modeling.** Simulated ORC performance shows **net efficiency of 5.75%**, turbine inlet/outlet flow consistency, and realistic pressure ratios - confirming proper coupling with the TCES discharge cycle. Although the electricity generation and efficiency of the ORC cycle installed at the discharge are limited, the cycle plays an important role by adapting the heat conditions coming from the TCES to the temperatures and requirements suitable for the district heating network.
- **The presence of an existing connection to the district heating network.** This further facilitates the integration of the RESTORE solution in this specific use case. This infrastructure significantly reduces the complexity and cost associated with establishing the necessary distribution system for thermal energy
- **Storage capacity as the limiting factor in TCES waste heat utilization.** The utilization of waste heat is primarily limited by the storage capacity of the thermochemical material (TCM), rather than by the availability of energy itself. This fact has a direct and positive impact on the viability of thermochemical storage

(TCES) projects, particularly those involving shorter charge-discharge cycles. In such cases, a greater share of the available waste heat can be effectively harnessed.

General conclusions are:

- **Gmunden Cement Plant as a suitable site for RESTORE Implementation.** The analysis conducted confirms the Gmunden Cement Plant as a highly suitable site for the implementation of waste heat recovery and TCES technologies. The combination of stable industrial processes, significant amounts of unused waste heat, and compatibility with district heating demands makes the plant an ideal candidate for the RESTORE use case. These findings validate its potential for supporting efficient, sustainable energy solutions through TCES integration.
- **$\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ confirmed as a viable TCM for DH-scaled systems.** The material shows high conversion efficiency in dehydration, stable cycling, and significant temperature lift ($>60^\circ\text{C}$), making it suitable for seasonal storage applications.
- **RESTORE Solution for waste heat recovery and district heating support.** The solution proposed and adapted to the use case described, successfully takes advantage of an energetically intensive industry waste heat, storing it form of chemical energy, and releasing it when needed into a district heating. The solution fully satisfies the energetic necessities of the district heating during the cement plant-shutdown coinciding with the discharging period.

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